

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF FERRIC—*p*-AMINOSALICYLATE COMPLEX

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The nature of Fe^{3+} —*p*-aminosalicylate complex has been studied spectrophotometrically. At pH 2.5 the complex contains one atom of Fe(III) and one molecule of *p*-aminosalicylic acid. The association constant of the complex has been determined at ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2M. By empirical extrapolation the thermodynamic association constant has been found to be 3.72×10^4 at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Phenols, phenolic acids and aminophenols form intense violet-coloured complexes with trivalent iron. The nature of some of these complexes has been studied by pH titrations. Only a few of these have been studied, however, by spectrophotometry. Ferric—salicylate complex was studied by Babko (*Zhur. Obscher. Khim.*, 1948, 18, 1617) and ferric—sulphosalicylate complex by Anderson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195). Both the workers report the formation of a complex with metal ion to ligand in the molecular ratio of 1:1 at lower pH. At higher pH, the colour of the solution changes, indicating formation of complexes with metal to ligand in molecular ratios of 1:2 and 1:3. Spectrophotometric method cannot, however, be used at high pH on account of hydrolysis of Fe(III) to a colloidal condition.

Ferric ion also forms a violet complex with *p*-aminosalicylic acid, sodium salt of which has been used more recently for colorimetric estimation of iron (Mukherjee, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 273) and gravimetric estimation of copper, mercury, bismuth, silver, and cerium (*Chem. Abst.*, 1950, 11877; Suranova and Olenovich, *Trudi Odesk Univ., Sbornik. Khim. Fak.*, 1953, 3, 71). Recently Agren (*Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 1059) has studied the complex formation between Fe^{3+} and some phenolic acids. He investigated the nature of *p*-aminosalicylic acid and its Fe(III) complex photometrically and potentiometrically. The photometric determination was done only at one ionic strength, namely in 3M sodium perchlorate medium. In the present work a detailed study of the ferric—*p*-aminosalicylate complex has been done spectrophotometrically. The stability constant has been determined at different ionic strengths so as to get an idea of the thermodynamic stability constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric perchlorate was prepared by dissolving the reagent grade iron powder in dilute perchloric acid (E. Merck, G. R.) and oxidising the ferrous perchlorate formed with hydrogen peroxide. The absence of ferrous ion in solution was tested by *o*-phenanthroline. The pH of the stock solution was found to be 1.78. Iron was estimated iodometrically (Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1946, 2nd ed., p. 356; Patnaik *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 25, 55).

Rhodia's reagent grade sodium salt of *p*-aminosalicylic acid was used as the ligand. The sample was purified by crystallisation and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The salt was found more stable than the acid in solution (cf. Agren, *Farm. Revy*, 1955, 54, 225).

Sodium perchlorate of B.D.H. pure quality was used to maintain the ionic strength. Perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide used were of E. Merck's G. R. quality. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

For the measurement of optical density a Hilger-Watt "UVISPEK" spectrophotometer of type H 700-303 was used. In absence of any arrangement for thermostating in the instrument used, all measurements were done at room temperature ($30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$).

The absorption measurements were taken in clean quartz cells of 1 cm path length. To avoid any possible error, caused by non-matching, readings were taken with cells interchanged. Each reading was taken with two different solutions. The slit width was kept fixed at 0.01 mm. This corresponds to a band width of 5 Å.

The pH of the solutions was measured with a Marconi pH meter (model TF 511 D). In the present case, pH was adjusted at 2.5 by mixing the reactants at definite proportions and making the volume to 100 c.c. A known volume of the above solution was taken and its pH measured. The acid or alkali as required were added dropwise to adjust the pH at 2.5. Knowing the actual number of drops of acid or alkali required to adjust the pH, the same solution was prepared and the required number of drops of acid or alkali added before dilution. Each solution was prepared in duplicate with adjusted pH, and its absorbance measured within a few hours of its preparation.

DISCUSSION

Although ferric perchlorate and sodium salt of *p*-aminosalicylic acid individually do not exhibit any absorption in the wave length region used, a solution containing both has an absorption maximum at 500 mμ. To ascertain the stability of the colour developed by the mixed solution of the two, its optical density was measured for a few hours at an interval of half an hour. Intensity of the colour developed did not change in 4 to 5 hours.

Molecular Composition of the Complex.—The molecular composition of the complex at pH 2.5 was determined by using Job's method of continued variation (Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113; 1936, xi, 6, 97; Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437). The absorption spectra of solutions containing different proportions of ferric perchlorate and P.A.S., adjusted at pH 2.5, were run over a range of 400–600 mμ. The total molarities of the solutions were kept constant; in the present case at $0.4795 \times 10^{-3}M$, $0.7192 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $0.3596 \times 10^{-3}M$. The figure gives the Job's curve at 500 mμ. The same also has been drawn at wave lengths 400 mμ to 600 mμ at an interval of 20 mμ. In the curves the positions of the maxima suggest the presence of 1 : 1 complex at the pH concerned. That the peaks of all the curves remain the same indicates the probable presence of only one complex in the solution.

FIG. 1

Extinction Coefficients.—Ferric perchlorate and P.A.S. were mixed in ratios of 1 : 9, 1 : 10, 1 : 12, etc. so that the latter always existed in excess, as any excess of the former had an oxidising influence. The pH of the solutions was adjusted at 2.5, and absorbance measured at 500 mμ.

On assuming that the complex formation was complete, the concentration of the complex was taken to be equal to that of ferric perchlorate, and the extinction coefficient calculated from Beer's law. The mean extinction coefficient value of the complex at 500 m μ was found to be $1675 \pm 7^\circ$.

Equilibrium Constant of the Complex.—Absorption measurements of the mixed solutions with pH were made for the quantitative determination of the stability constant. The ionic strengths of the solutions were taken to be equal to the concentrations of sodium perchlorate as it was always present in large quantities as compared to other components.

From the continued variation curve it is apparent that the complex is formed by the combination of Fe³⁺ and P.A.S. in molecular ratio of 1:1. Since the dissociation constant of the -COOH group in the ligand is $10^{-4.08}$ ("Stability Constants. Part I", the Chemical Society, London, special publication No. 6, p. 57) at pH 2.5, the acid will exist to a large extent in the dissociated form as

The equilibrium between Fe³⁺ and P.A.S. may be written as

The formation constant K' can be written as

$$K' = \frac{[\text{FeR}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HR}^-]}$$

or when $[\text{H}^+]$ is fixed, we have $\frac{[\text{FeR}]}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HR}^-]}$ to be constant. $[\text{HR}^-]$ may be taken as $\{[\text{HR}^-]_{\text{total}} - [\text{HR}^-]_{\text{bound}}\}$. If, however, one takes into account the fact that the ligand may not exist totally as $[\text{HR}^-]$, it can be shown that

$$\{[\text{H}_2\text{R}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{FeR}]\} = [\text{HR}^-] \left\{ \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1} + 1 + \frac{K_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \right\} \text{ where } K_1 \text{ and } K_2 \text{ are}$$

dissociation constants for $\text{H}_2\text{R} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{HR}^-$ and $\text{HR} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{R}^{2-}$ respectively. So

$$\frac{[\text{FeR}]}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}]_{\text{free}} \{[\text{H}_2\text{R}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{FeR}]\}}$$

is constant at a constant pH. In our calculation of the association constant, we have used this expression. The various terms in the expression are obtained in the following way. $[\text{FeR}]$ is calculated from the measured optical density of the solution containing the metal ion and the ligand, using Beer's law, the extinction coefficient of the complex species having been known. The total concentrations of the metal ion and the ligand are known and, hence the concentration terms in the denominator. Thus, all the terms being known, the association constant is calculated.

The results recorded in Table I show one typical reading for each ionic strength. At each ionic strength about ten sets of readings with different amounts of ligand and metal ion have been taken. The average value of the association constant with standard deviations has been noted. The

association constants are $(3.06 \pm 0.06) \times 10^4$, $(2.56 \pm 0.12) \times 10^4$, $(2.37 \pm 0.12) \times 10^4$ and $(2.21 \pm 0.11) \times 10^4$ at ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 respectively. An attempt has been made to get the thermodynamic association constant by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. Since none of the extrapolations, either $\log K$ against μ (ionic strength) or $\log K$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ give a linear extrapolation, the value of $\log K$ at $\mu=0$ has been obtained by both the methods of extrapolation. The average value is 3.72×10^4 .

TABLE I

Molarity ($\times 10^4$) of Fe (ClO_4) ₃	P.A.S.	Ionic strength.	Optical density.	$K \times 10^{-4}$	No of readings taken with diff. conc. of reactants.	Average $K \times 10^{-4}$.
2.677	2.397	0.02	0.3059	3.05	9	3.06 ± 0.06
4.795	4.795	0.05	0.6077	2.66	9	2.56 ± 0.12
3.356	2.397	0.10	0.3105	2.27	9	2.37 ± 0.12
2.677	1.918	0.20	0.2395	2.02	9	2.21 ± 0.11

As mentioned earlier, Agren (*loc. cit.*) made a quantitative study of the Fe^{3+} —P.A.S. system. He kept the ionic strength of the medium fixed at 3M. So a quantitative comparison of our results with his is not possible. A semiquantitative comparison can, however, be made. Agren found the violet complex to be composed of one atom of iron and one molecule of P.A.S. In our experiments at pH 2.5, the continued variation curve at different wave lengths indicates the complex to possess a molecular ratio of 1 : 1. It may be mentioned here that the species FeRH would also give a maximum in Job's curve at 1 : 1. But the species FeRH is probably not present, or even if it is there, the concentration is negligibly small because the dissociation of the H_3R^+ will be almost complete at pH 2.5 for $pK_{a_1} = 2.0\%$ (*loc. cit.*). So we assume that the complex is only FeR . To get an idea as to how far the association constant in the present determination and that of Agren agree, we have calculated the value of the

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{R}^{2-}]}{[\text{FeR}]}$$

from our results. Using the different stages of equilibrium of the dissociation of the ligand ($pK_{a_1} = 2.08$, $pK_1 = 4.08$, $pK_2 = 13.74$; *loc. cit.*) it can be easily shown that the present association constant is related to

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{R}^{2-}]}{[\text{FeR}]}$$

as in the equations :

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \left\{ [\text{H}_2\text{R}]_T - [\text{FeR}] \right\}}{[\text{FeR}]} = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{R}^{2-}] \left\{ \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2} + 1 \right\}}{[\text{FeR}]} \quad \dots (1)$$

when the dissociation of the -COOH and -OH groups of the ligand are considered ; or

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{R}^{2-}]}{[\text{FeR}]} \left\{ \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_{a_1} K_1 K_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2} + 1 \right\} \quad \dots (2)$$

when the dissociation of -NH₃⁺, -COOH and -OH groups are considered. From our measurements, the value of

$$\frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{R}^{2-}]}{[\text{FeR}]}$$

at ionic strength 0.2 *M* comes out to be 0.76×10^{-17} and 0.43×10^{-17} on the basis of equations (1) and (2) respectively. The value reported by Agren is 1.07×10^{-17} at ionic strength 3 *M*. The effect of increase in ionic strength has a tendency to increase the dissociation constant by decreasing the activity of the ionic species. So qualitatively the trend is correct, although it is very difficult to suggest how far quantitatively such high ionic strength of the medium should increase the value of dissociation constant. However, the order of agreement is satisfying.

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